

Goddess Viśālākṣī:

The Case for a Great Goddess Tradition

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Abstract: This paper attempts to explore the religion and (almost irretrievably lost) history of the Goddess Viśālākṣī, while making cross-references to the relevant myth, theology, iconography, rituals, sacred incantations and folk traditions of the Goddess which might illuminate our understanding of Her cult. There is a genuine research gap about this Goddess which this paper aims to address. Worshipped as the Great Goddess by some of the Śāktas, and as a folk goddess by the common people, Her cult is widely prevalent in the Rāḍḍha region of Bengal, but is not just limited to it. This paper aims to present what the title of this paper calls a case for Viśālākṣī cult as a Great Goddess tradition. She is a folk goddess residing at the margins, but She is also mentioned as a Great Goddess and a Mahāvidyā in some texts, and She is the reigning deity of Kāśī, the orthodox centre of Hinduism. She is a conglomerate of strange paradoxes. Goddess Viśālākṣī frustrates neat categorizations. Her diverse folk nomenclatures in Bengal have been uniformly Sanskritized into Viśālākṣī, but in spite of that, Her myriad names continue to persist, which are only matched by Her iconological variations. She might represent the remnants of an ancient Great Goddess tradition which though now forgotten, once might have defined the Goddess Religions of antiquity. Thus, the figure of Goddess Viśālākṣī may signify the resurrection of archaic Great Goddess cults. This paper analyses a collage of textual evidences as well as lived traditions, scrutinizing past accounts as well as conducting case studies and field visits to reconstruct the trajectory of the cult of the Goddess Viśālākṣī as a Great Goddess.

Keywords: Śākta Religion, Tantra, Śaktism, Bengal Goddesses, Great Goddess, Great Goddess Tradition, Viśālākṣī, Biśālokkhī, Viśālākṣmī, Bāśulī, Bāśalī, Viśālākṣmī/Manasā, Lakṣmī, Sarasvatī, Kālī, Vārāhī, Water Goddess, Earth Goddess, Wealth Goddess, Cāmuṇḍā, Saptamātrkā, Mahāvidyā, Viśāla Lakṣmī, Viśāla Yakṣī, Alakṣmī (Non- Lakṣmī), Jyeṣṭhyā Lakṣmī, Ādi Lakṣmī, Viṣa Lakṣmī, Chandraketugarh Gangaridai Civilization, Vajrayāna, Sahajayāna, Vaiṣṇavism, Folk Studies, New Great Goddess, Old Great Goddess.

“Viśvarupe Viśālākṣi vidyāṃ dehi namostute”

(Appearing as the World, O large eyed lady, may You please give knowledge, I bow to You)

--- Hymn to the Goddess Sarasvatī (translation mine)

“[O]ld gods never die.”

--- Sukumar Sen

Prolegomenon

Sukumar Sen states that Great Goddesses like Manasā and Bāsulī became outcast and eclipsed during the Middle Ages, but then came back in a revived form during the early modern era, and to explain this phenomenon, he quotes an English idiom, “old gods never die”, observing that “Kālī-Bāsulī reappeared in the eighteenth century in newer forms” (*Prabandhasaṃkalana third vol 5*). He does not elaborate his pithy observation any further, and that is a pity, because the specific events of the Middle Ages leading to the eclipse of the Goddess cults, and those of the eighteenth century leading to the rerise of Goddess cults do merit detailed discussions to illuminate our understanding of the Goddess trajectory in Bengal. But Sen might not be mistaken in his observation about the eclipse and revival of the Goddess cults.

Our chronicled history does illustrate the decline of the Goddess cults during the late medieval period, which may be attributed to the loss of royal patronage and power equations supporting the Goddess religions and Tantrism in Bengal during this time as the Turco-Afghan invasion took place. Professor Gavin Flood in one of his lectures delivered as a part of the Tantra course in Oxford Centre for Hindu Studies maintains that royal patronage to Tantra was crucial for its position as state religion during the early medieval era, but this was no longer the case during the late medieval era (“Tantra: A New Understanding”), following the beginning of Islamic rule.

Similarly, we may propose that the massive rerise of the Goddess cults during the early modern period of eighteenth century might have been caused by a plethora of factors including the royal patronage of Śākta rulers like King Kṛṣṇacandra of Nadia and Śākta Sādhakas like Rāmaprasāda and Kamalākānta. Of course, such periodic eclipses and revivals might be categorized as epiphenomenon, and deeper socio-cultural and economic factors responsible for the recession and reemergence of the Goddess cults during different historical periods still remain to be discussed. Moreover, in all probability, Goddess cults within the popular domain of the folk cultures always continued to thrive, even without royal patronage, as the communities did always celebrate their guardian goddesses.

Going back to the statement of Sukumar Sen, the hyphenation he puts to bring together Kālī and Bāsulī implies that he looks at the revival of the worship of Goddess Bāsulī/Viśālākṣī to have been closely aligned with the cult of Kālī. Sen probably proposes that Goddess Bāsulī is equated with the supreme Goddess, as She becomes hyphenated with Kālī, the Great Goddess for Bengali Śāktas. This is an interesting line of enquiry which we shall explore in this article.

For Her devotees, She may be the supreme and sovereign deity ruling over the entire world, but for others, Viśālākṣī may be a marginal and local goddess, barely mentioned in the orthodox Hindu scriptures, mostly ignored by the Sāvārṇa elites, and Her cult may be described as a mere folk religion. Viśālākṣī is not a Mahāvidyā as per the mainstream Daśa Mahāvidyā pantheon of Bengal which can be found in Bṛhaddharmapurāṇa, composed during the Sena period in the twelfth century. And yet, in Abhinavagupta’s disciple Kṣemarāja’s (eleventh-century commentary on) *Mālinīvijayatantra* mentions Goddess Bāsalī prominently among the Mahāvidyās: She is addressed as "mahāvidyā mahītale" and "kalaupūrṇaphalapradāḥ" which signifies that as a mahāvidyā the Goddess blesses the earth as the giver of complete fruits (of desire) to the devotees in the age of Kali (Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya 331). This eleventh century mention could be the earliest recorded reference to the Goddess Bāsalī.

Sahaja Tantra might have been a crucial religious ambience in which the Great Goddess Viśālākṣī thrived. The medieval Sahajiyā poet of Bengali literature, legendary author of Śrīkrṣṇakīrtana, Baḍu Caṇḍīdāsa who identifies himself both as *Baḍu* (the term denotes a Brahmin in the service of deity) as well as *Bāsalīgaṇa*, or the attendant of the Goddess Bāsalī (Sukumar Sen *Vol 1: 377*), these two epithets being the significant personal identifiers the poet uses about himself, was undoubtedly a devotee of the Goddess Bāsalī, or Viśālākṣī.

Sen firmly advocates that the Goddess Bāsulī is associated with Sahaja (*first vol 389*). Sahaja literally means what one is born with, but the term commonly means lucid or easy. Sahaja was a protestant form of Tantra which denounced scriptural and ritual complexity and emphasized the lucid path of liberation. which became prevalent in Bengal during the Pāla period (refer to Alaka Chattopadhyay's work on the 84 siddhas).

Sukumar Sen uses two different variants of the name of this Goddess, unaware of this discrepancy within a single article, as in this article, compiled in the first volume of his *Prabandhasamgraha*, he first speaks of Bāsalī (377), and then Bāsulī (389-90). These unwitting variations in the name of the Goddess in Sen's article occur, curiously enough, while discussing the problematics of various poets sharing the same name of Caṇḍīdāsa.

Chhatna's Bāsulī temple is proposed to be the site of the legendary poet's creative meditations as it houses the guardian goddess Bāsulī, whose iconography matches the scripturally common form of Khaḍga-khetaka-dhāriṇī, but Sukumar Sen believes that this is an invented tradition of relatively later provenance which connects the poet to Chhatna, and instead advocates for Nanoor, Birbhum as the actual site of the legendary poet's flourish, which also has a temple where we find Bāsulī, whose iconography however does not match the commonly known form, that is the Nanoor Bāsulī is not Khaḍga-khetaka-dhāriṇī, and is rather caturbhujā vīṇāpāṇī, a form of the Goddess Saraswati with four arms. Sen's article is on the problematics of multiple Caṇḍīdāsas, but appropriately enough, it briefly brings us to the essential paradox of the Goddess Viśālākṣī.

In this article Sen laments that the Tāntrika forms of Goddess iconographies and methods of worship prevalent in Bengal have not yet been closely studied, but due to the same reason, any iconological attempt to disprove Nanoor Bāsulī as the original deity worshipped by Caṇḍīdāsa will be futile (*first vol 390*). The orthography, iconography, theology, ritual practices of this "Great" (literally the first part of her name, Viśāla signifies largeness) Goddess remain mysteriously myriad.

One: Case Study & Field Visit of Viśālākṣī Temples

Sadly, no comprehensive academic work has been undertaken on Goddess Viśālākṣī so far to the best of my knowledge. Even no complete list of Viśālākṣī temples of Bengal is available anywhere. The Goddess is predominant in Rāḍha Bengal. Her cult is strikingly preponderant in Hooghly district. But She is worshipped in many other places across the Bengali speaking regions, which can be diverse and different from each other. There are Viśālākṣī temples in South 24 Parganas, in the southernmost tip of Gangetic delta. I have been privy to the fact that Her worship might be taking place in the Barak valley in North East India too, where I once found a derelict Goddess idol by the wayside at a place called Durgakona (near Assam University), which was probably discarded after worship, which though at a first glance looked

like Kālī, nonetheless shared iconographic similarities with Goddess Viśālākṣī, particularly the presence of two prostrate Bhairavas, one of whom was ritually decapitated (figure 1). Not very far this place is the seat of the guardian deity of Cachar, the Great Goddess called Kācākānti (originally a tribal Goddess named Kechai Khati; the name means that the Goddess loved to eat raw meat). Kācākānti could be a form of Viśālākṣī too, I suggest (figure 2). As a rule of thumb, any Goddess whose iconography looks like Kālī but has a non-dark complexion, or is accompanied by two Bhairavas could be akin to Viśālākṣī. Her tremendous local variations can be explained by the folklorist concept of oicotype, we may argue. She belongs with the masses, while her presence is registered in the canonical literature too. Who is this Goddess? She is an inspirer of great Bengali poets Caṇḍīdāsa and Kamalakanta, but literature about Her is scanty.

Understanding this Goddess is not possible through scriptural study alone, because scriptures are just sketchy when it comes to this Goddess. They do not give us any details about the lived traditions of Her cult, and leave much to be desired. Therefore, field visits are a must. Shibshankar Bharati's popular non-academic book *Bāṅglāra Prācīna Kālīkathā* describes historical and legendary details of a number of Kālī temples of Bengal. In this book he recounts his visits to a total of eight Viśālākṣī temples (so here again we find Viśālākṣī-Kālī hyphenation, because Viśālākṣī is considered by this author as a form of Kālī) across five districts, namely Birbhum, Bardhaman, Hooghly, Howrah and North 24 Parganas (303-335), but this field work is by no means exhaustive. For example, he misses out the very crucial and famous temple of Viśālākṣī at Chhatna, Bankura district, and the equally famous Viśālākṣī temple at Sinhet, Hooghly district, just to quote two random examples. Later in this article I shall produce the list of Viśālākṣī sites which Shibshankar Bharati describes.

A Visit to Viśālākṣī Temple at Channa village, Bardhaman

The temple of the Goddess here is explicitly identified as Viśālākṣī Kālī temple (figure 3), as my field visit revealed, which may not just be due to its association with the poet-sage Kamalākānta who attained Śākta Tāntrika enlightenment (siddhi) here, seated on his Tāntrika throne of the five skulls (Pañcamuṇḍī Āsana), which makes it a siddhapīṭha or a sacred site of attainment, where some of the most memorable Bengali hymns to the Goddess Kālī were composed, but may also validate Sukumar Sen's observation noted earlier in our prolegomenon. Today a statue of Kamalākānta stands on this Pañcamuṇḍī, which is located on the back side of the main temple (figure 4). This Pañcamuṇḍī Āsana or the Throne of five skulls, is a particular kind of Tāntrika couch, where the skulls of a human (Caṇḍāla, who did not die a natural death, but rather died owing to some accident), a fox, a monkey, a snake and a mongoose are buried beneath the ground.

As per my observation, the aniconic idol of the Goddess Viśālākṣī at the Channa temple consists of five Lakṣmī ghaṭas, or ritual vessels (earthen pots) which commonly stand for the bounty of the Goddess Lakṣmī. These ghaṭas have been perforated and decorated to resemble faces with eyes and mouths, so as to represent the heads of the Goddess, so they have become semi-iconic. For the same reason immediate recognition of them as Lakṣmī ghaṭas may not be possible without careful scrutiny. The five heads probably represent the different elements within the philosophical system of enumeration in Sāṃkhya and Tantra. They can also signify the one Great Goddess surrounded by four attendant deities. I was told that photography of the idol was prohibited, when I went there, so I desisted from taking any photos of the sanctum sanctorum.

I observed that there are two Bhairava temples on two corners of the main temple of the Goddess Viśālākṣī at Channa, aptly positioned as the Dvārapāla or guardians of the gates. As the Goddess is aniconic in this temple, Bhairavas too are aniconic. Interestingly one of the Bhairavas is identified with Marang Buru, a God of the Santhal tribe, to whom the boar sacrifices are offered on the annual day of worship, which might have been a Brahminical compromise, a clever ploy to invite and invoke an external deity as a justification of a primitive custom of ritual sacrifice of an ‘unclean’ animal, often associated with oppressed castes like Bāgdī, which could no longer be accommodated within the orthodox scheme of worship. The ritual sacrifice of boars is mentioned by Bharati who quotes Jogendranath Gupta on this matter (330), and the fact was corroborated by the locals during my visit too. During recent innovation, top of the Bhairava temple which stands by the side of main entrance has been given the appearance of a Śivaliṅga. Boar sacrifice takes place not at this temple, but at the Bhairava temple on the rear side. Little horse figurines are found inside both the Bhairava temples, which is a curious practice as mainstream Hindu Gods in Bengal are rarely associated with horses, while it has been a dominant insignia of Muslim preachers of the medieval times (the practice of offering horse figurines is called *chalāna*). However, some rural communities of Bengal do use horse figurines for religious purposes (figures 5a, 5b, 5c).

The annual worship and public festival of Goddess Viśālākṣī at Channa village in Bardhaman takes place during the Vārāhī Navarātri or Āṣāḍha Navarātri, also called Gupta (secret) Navarātri or Tāntrika Navarātri, which consist of the first nine nights of the lunar fortnight in the monsoon month of Āṣāḍha culminating in the full moon. This annual worship of the Goddess is held on the ninth day of the Āṣāḍha Śukla Pakṣa fortnight. For those who are unfamiliar with the Tāntrika calendar of the nine days of Goddess Vārāhī, this is the same fortnight when the chariot festival of Jagannātha takes place, whereas this annual day of worship of Viśālākṣī is on the ninth day, that coincides with the day before Ulto Roth (day of the return of Jagannātha chariot, the tenth day). This aspect might be significant, because this opens up the possibility of some early Vaiṣṇava associations with Goddess Vārāhī. This Goddess was appropriated by early Vaiṣṇavism as the Śakti of Varāha Avatāra, and in that capacity regularly features in the Saptamātrkā pantheon. The Boar Goddess also entered the pantheon of Tāntrika Buddhism as Vajravārāhī.

The Boar Goddess might have been a very ancient deity. According to Haripriya Rangarajan, certain sources depict Her as the Mother of all creation (Her pot belly signifying the primordial womb that gave rise to the world) and not a mere consort of Varāha that the Goddess becomes later during the Purāṇic period; in the same vein, Rangarajan notes that in this capacity the Boar Goddess is called Jyeṣṭhā, or the Eldest Goddess (48), which, we may observe, is an epithet always meant for the elder Lakṣmī, also called Alakṣmī, a Goddess generally feared but also revered in Orthodox Hinduism. This is an important fact, to which we shall return later.

The boar totem is very old in South Asia, and was present in the Copper Hoard Culture which arose after the collapse of the Harappan civilization, and one such depiction of the Boar deity (‘pregnant’?) with the Harappan unicorn in its belly can fascinate us (figure 6). Boar worship might have a lineage far older than we commonly ascribe to the presence of Vārāhī in the Saptamātrkā pantheon during the Purāṇic period. Pala period iconography of Goddess Vārāhī depicts the deity as carrying fish in Her hands (figure 7), while some iconographic details from other parts of India often depict the Boar Goddess to be riding a buffalo (figure 8). The

Goddess's prominent iconological associations with fish and buffalo, two important insignia of the Harappan world might allude to archaic remnants of ancient cults of South Asia.^{End Note 1}

In spite of being a sovereign Creatrix Goddess of antiquity, early Vaiṣṇavism appropriated this Boar Goddess as the Vaiṣṇava consort (Rangarajan 36ff). We shall note here that in Her earlier form, Goddess Lakṣmī too was a Sovereign Creatrix and a Great Goddess, and She was not always merely a consort Goddess. Lakṣmī was not an exclusive feature of Vaiṣṇavism either, and was there in early Śaivism, as well as in Buddhism and Jainism.^{End Note 2}

Vārāhī is generally the Earth Goddess, and the time of monsoon stands for fertility and abundance. I find a prevalent legend and anecdote about Kamalākānta offering fish to the Goddess in this temple which might pertinently illustrate an ancient custom. As the fish symbol generally represented the water deity since the early antiquity of the bronze age civilizations (refer to aforementioned End Note 1), therefore the theology of Goddess Vārāhī might represent the confluence of Earth and Water. Further, the tantalizing confluence of a Tāntrika form of early Vaiṣṇavism and the Goddess cult can be seen in the iconology and mythology of Goddess Vārāhī. Interestingly, boars are sacrificed on the day of the annual festival of Goddess Viśālākṣī in this temple at Channa, which again might be significant. We may conclude that certain rites, rituals and customs of the cult of Viśālākṣī contain remnants from the now forgotten but once predominant Vārāhī cult, the theology of which celebrated the confluence of earth and water.

The temple priests are Brahmins, and the post of the priest is hereditary, with a few families of Brahmins in perpetual service to the deity. Certain events during the Saturday prayer service that I witnessed seemed to suggest that this Brahminization of the Goddess cult is still an ongoing, incomplete and fragile process.^{End Note 3}

The temple becomes deserted by the afternoon, and as per the admission of the priest, he would not venture near the temple during night. Multiple anecdotes corroborate this nocturnal terror of the Viśālākṣī temple at Channa village. The temple compound has a prominent waterbody, from where the Great Goddess Herself in the guise of a Bāgdī lady once fetched fishes for Kamalākānta, who regularly made the offerings of fish to the deity, but due to some reason did not acquire the sacrificial fish on that day, so after nightfall the Goddess Herself came to him in the form of a lady from the 'untouchable' Bāgdī caste, as per one popular legend. Diptimoy Roy makes a passing allusion to this legend without giving any details (243). This legend both establishes and deconstructs the element of nocturnal terror. As the Goddess Herself might roam here during the night, the temple compound might indeed become a site of sacred terror. But by the same token, this is also a site of Tāntrika enlightenment. At night, the temple compound might become off limits for any form of Āryāvarta patriarchy and casteism which appropriate the Goddess during the day.

A Visit to Vana Viśālākṣī Temple in the village Nasibpur, Hooghly

The Goddess, whose name is often uttered and spelled as Bono Biśālökkhī (in Sanskrit that would be Vana Viśālākṣmī) by the locals, is worshipped inside an empty temple here. The locals almost always pronounce the name of the Goddess as Biśālökkhi, thus phonetically connecting the Goddess Viśālākṣī to Goddess Lakṣmī. It is pertinent to note that in the Eastern Indian Prakrit and in Bengali, Lakṣmī is pronounced Lokkhi: though spelled Lakṣmī, but always pronounced Lokkhi in Bengali (Lakkhī in Prakrit) which could be spelled as Lakṣī in the

Pali/Prakrit languages, and this spelling might have been at the roots of the Sanskritized name of the Goddess who was always the Great Lakkhī or Biśālakkhī (figure 9), but then was Sanskritized into the Goddess with Large Eyes or Viśālākṣī. This is a fruitful line of thinking, as the Goddess Viśālākṣī is explicitly identified with the Goddess Lakṣmī by Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya who makes the following observation: “In the dhyānamantra of Tantrasāra the Goddess Bāsulī is the giver of all fortune and wealth. Mukunda Mishra (writer of Bāsulīmaṅgala) attributes the Goddess with lotus abode. In Dharmapujā scriptures, the Goddess rises on the banks of the river or shore of the sea. Therefore, the Goddess Bāsulī is seemingly the form of Lakṣmī” (330). The Great Lakṣmī (Viśālākṣmī) perhaps is a remnant of a Goddess tradition which resisted patriarchal appropriation, unlike Lakṣmī who got tamed by various patriarchal religions.

While the local nomenclature identifies the Goddess here as the great goddess of the wealth of forests and woodlands (Bono Biśālakkhī), the emptiness of the temple either remains another instance of the aniconic worship of the Goddess, or an example of the resilience of the cult, in case the original idol was stolen or destroyed, because in spite of the absence of idol, daily worship never stopped in this empty temple as per local accounts, as the author found out during the field visit (figure 10). Stories of nocturnal terror can be found here just like the Channa temple, as this temple is also deserted at night. There is also a waterbody near the temple which is said to be frequented by the Goddess at night. An obstruction in the path of the nocturnal walk of the Goddess from the waterbody to the temple, which was once caused by a businessman, led to fearful consequences, local legends point out. The temple, made of terracotta, is at least a few centuries old, but renovation is fearfully avoided, and again there are local legends which observe that any restructuring of the temple premises is prohibited under fear of pain and death. The Goddess here evokes fear. By the same token She is Jāgrata, or a Goddess who is ever awake.

Waterbodies are usually important for Goddess Viśālākṣī. A popular legend about the revival of the Nanor Viśālākṣī again connects the Goddess to a waterbody. According to the legend, the Goddess got hidden and forgotten inside a mound following the death of Caṇḍīdāsa. Eventually the Goddess revealed Herself to a lady from the Tili community (artisan community who extracted seed oil), following which the water from a sacred pond named Sarojā (literally meaning Lotus) blessed by the Goddess turned into seed oil. The story is recounted by Bharati (306).

Two: A Case for Lakṣmī?

Alakṣmī (Non- Lakṣmī) is a Goddess mentioned in Mahābhārata, and She is connected with Kālī (Bikas Bhattacharya 21). Further, in forgotten antiquity, references to the Goddess Lakṣmī were ambivalent, and one scholarly suggestion is that Lakṣmī was originally a corpse disease later transformed into Alakṣmī (Mayer, qtd. in Bikas Bhattacharya 12). In Atharvaveda, Lakṣmī is ambivalent and represents both fortune and misfortune (Bikas Bhattacharya 11).

A scholar of Goddess religions must resist the temptation to speculate that the figure of Goddess Viśālākṣī might be an archaic Great Goddess, worshipped since earliest antiquity in an unchanged form. There may be substantial factors behind such temptations. Among the common people of Bengal, the Goddess is most prominently worshipped by the Kaivarta

community (a foundational Caste in Bengali population traditionally engaged with fishing), as suggested by Gopendrakrishna Basu in his study of Viśālākṣī as a folk goddess (66). The Kaivarta community is indeed quite ancient and might have dominated the riverine Gangetic delta since earliest antiquity. Some recensions of *Mahābhārata* record the existence of the Karvaṭa Janapada (which might be associated with the archaic Kaivarta people) in Southern Bengal during the martial expedition of Bhīma when he subdued Tāmralipta, Karvaṭa and Suhma. ^{End Note 4}

This is a temptation which the scholar of the Goddess religions must resist, because in spite of some of the distinctly antiquated elements detected in the cult of Goddess Viśālākṣī, there is sadly no unbroken lineage of this Goddess, the records of which we can trace back to ancient period. Rather, a more fruitful line of enquiry might consist of our ability to scrutinize the amalgamation of diverse and archaic threads of pre-existing Great Goddess religions and the existing marginal folk goddess cults which might have come together and constituted the trajectory of this cult of Goddess Viśālākṣī during the early and late medieval era right through the early modern era, as the records during these periods are available with us. We may propose that with the dissolution and appropriation of the primitive Great Goddess by various patriarchal religions, new Sovereign Great Goddesses was restructured from the fragments of the forgotten Great Goddesses of antiquity as well as the existing folk goddess cults. The periodic eclipse of the Great Goddess is followed by Her reemergence in newer ways, we may argue following Sukumar Sen.

Lakṣmī, as a Water Goddess, as a Fertility Goddess, as a Wealth Goddess, and somewhat outrageously as a Fish loving Goddess, not just from the forgotten antiquity but also within the lived traditions of Bengal (many households in Eastern Bengal observe the folk custom of offering a pair of Hilsa fishes to the Goddess Lakṣmī on the day of Kojāgarī Pūrṇimā, that is Śārādīya Pūrṇimā, the last day of Devīpakṣa, the lunar fortnight associated with autumnal Durgā Pujā, culminating on the auspicious full moon when Goddess Lakṣmī is worshipped), was an extremely important Great Goddess in the remote past, probably from the pre-Vedic times (refer to aforementioned End Note 2). And even after many centuries, we have archaeological evidence of the worship of a Great Goddess representing the principle of wealth, fertility and abundance in Chandraketurah Gangaridai civilization, by this time with all the familiar iconographic details which even today we associate with Lakṣmī (figure 11). We find a Goddess carrying a pair of fishes at Chandraketurah, not common in the worship of Lakṣmī any more, but not completely extinct either, as I just recorded above (figure 12).

Eventually, a disjunction came to Chandraketurah Gangaridai civilization, roughly 2000 years before present, from when the specific Goddesses worshipped in ancient Bengal are no longer found, as if an entire culture came to an end, and the unique Goddesses this culture worshipped simply vanished (for details refer to my article “Archaeology of Prakṛti”). It can be logically assumed that the archaic Great Goddesses might have been destroyed or appropriated by the newly incumbent patriarchal religions from Āryāvarta. This is somewhat in tune with Marija Gimbutas’s argument in *Civilizations of the Goddess* who maintains that the matrilineal cultures of Old Europe were overrun by the Kurgan culture, i.e. the patriarchal Indo-Europeans. Though the time frames of the dissolution of Old Europe and that of the Archaic Goddess cults of Ancient Bengal are very different, but then Bengal remained outside the pale of Āryāvarta for a very long time. Aryanization of Bengal happened much later in the historical period, Ramesh Chandra Majumdar maintains (25ff).

We never find the archaic Śrī/Lakṣmī/Wealth Goddess from Chandraketurgarh depicted as a consort. Her iconography is clearly that of a Sovereign Great Goddess. We may note here that this is how the Goddess is still worshipped in Bengali households: the iconography is that of a solitary deity, not that of a consort. However, during the Purāṇic era the Goddess Lakṣmī becomes a consort to the powerful male God Viṣṇu as per scriptures, subservient to such an extent that it would not be an exaggeration to say that the Great Goddess of antiquity was mutilated and fragmented by the patriarchy. This consort goddess is now popularly depicted massaging the feet of a resting Viṣṇu.

The present author would suggest that there is a strong possibility, that the fragments of the old Great Goddess cults continued their existence underground, went on to accumulate a momentum, in a spirit of dissidence and subversion against the incumbent male Godhead of Vedic and Purāṇic patriarchy, finally to give rise to a number of new Great Goddesses dominating the religious scene in eastern India during the post-Gupta period, that is, the early medieval period which also coincides with the emergence of the Tāntrika civilization of Gauḍa.

This is not to say that these newly emergent Great Goddesses were free from any patriarchal encroachments. The archaic Great Goddess was a Sovereign Creatrix, but the new Great Goddesses could not shake off the male Gods so easily whose supremacy was already accepted in society. Therefore, these new Great Goddesses often appeared as the supreme power of all the male Gods, and thus intelligently used the male Gods for the purpose of Goddess supremacy, and Śrī Śrī Caṇḍī (composed in sixth century approximately) would be a case in point.

Śrī Śrī Caṇḍī is a part of Mārkaṇḍeya Purāṇa, a Vaiṣṇava purāṇa, and the Goddess Durgā is, in spite of fulfilling most of the criteria of a Great Goddess, remains the Māyā (or the worldly power) of the Almighty male God Nārāyaṇa, and is repeatedly referred to as Nārāyaṇī in the hymns. A detailed discussion of this feature of the new Great Goddesses of the Tāntrika age, where She is both patriarchally appropriated and yet transcends the barriers of patriarchy, where the new Great Goddess cults carry out some rather innovative counter-appropriations of the male Gods, is tantalizingly beyond the scope of this article, so we must return to our discussion.

The point remains: a massive re-rise of Great Goddesses can be observed during this period: Hinduism had Durgā, Jainism Ambikā, Buddhism Tārā. The early medieval period witnesses the dawn of a Tāntrika age, which is the central thesis in Imma Ramos's *Tantra Enlightenment to Revolution*. Where did these new Great Goddesses appear from? This is a question we must ask, and a logical hypothesis would be the proposition that I defend in this article: that the cults of the new Great Goddesses were built on the ruins of the old Great Goddesses.

Here, I concur with Bikas Kumar Bhattacharya who maintains that a number of iconological and theological features of Goddess Tārā are taken from those of the (pre-existing) Goddess Śrī /Lakṣmī, and there is a specific Tāntrika text titled *Lakṣmītantra*, composed sometime between ninth and twelfth century AD, which explicitly puts forward this claim that Goddess Tārā is an incarnation of Goddess Lakṣmī (13). Any lay observer can identify the commonality of the presence of lotus in the respective iconographies of these two Goddesses, and any scholar of Goddess religions will be able to observe a number of nuanced connections between these two Goddesses. The very nomenclature of Goddess Tārā signifies a water goddess helping the devotees cross the ocean of time and space (Tāriṇī). Lakṣmī, as we know, was essentially a Water Goddess of antiquity, which is why the Purāṇas imagined the Goddess to be emerging

from the ocean churning (samudra manthana). Her features like wealth and abundance and fertility were connected to the Water of the seas and rivers.

But while the new Great Goddesses like Tārā and Durgā emerged from the ruins of the old Great Goddess with the active patronage of powerful mainstream religions like Tāntrika Buddhism and Tāntrika Hinduism, no such 'luck' was there for Goddess Viśālākṣī (though She was also appropriated as an Āvaraṇa Goddess to Dharma, as we shall see, but Dharma cult of Rāḍḥa was not a mainstream, organized patriarchal religion during the middle ages, and was itself marginal).

This factor probably explains why She remains marginal, often donning the hat of a folk deity. But precisely for that reason, Viśālākṣī merits our attention. This much we can say to the credit of the Viśālākṣī cult, that this new Great Goddess emerged during the medieval period (early to late) without being substantially aided by any organized mainstream patriarchal religion in this part of the world. She illustrates a return of the Great Goddess as Svayambhū and Sovereign, not a consort. Her familiar iconography in Bengal depict the Goddess with two Bhairavas, both of whom remain prostrate and abject by Her feet.

This iconography ensured that Goddess Viśālākṣī could not be turned into a consort goddess. As Marija Gimbutas has time and again emphasized, the old Great Goddesses from the archaic past did not impose a matriarchy (a mirror image of oppression like patriarchy), and instead assigned crucial places to men. The Bhairavas of Viśālākṣī can be seen as a compromise with the age of patriarchy by some scholars, but the iconographic detail convinces me that the Goddess idol might carry the potential seeds of the reemergence of the old Great Goddesses. Lastly, Sukumar Sen emphasized the fact that Goddess Viśālākṣī is a virgin Goddess embodying eternal youth, as She is depicted to be perennially sixteen years old (*third vol* 259-60). The indication is that as a forever virgin Goddess, She is not a consort.

Three: The Sacred Sites of Rāḍḥa

Bāśulī is prominently mentioned in Dharmapujā vidhāna as one of the Āvaraṇa (literally, veil; by extension, protector guardian) deities of Dharma, and as such is professed to be identical with Maṅgala Caṇḍī, which suggests that Tāntrika Buddhism in Rāḍḥa Bengal attempted to appropriate the Goddess (Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya 328). Worship of Dharma was predominant in Rāḍḥa Bengal during medieval period, and this cult was derived from Buddhism, as per scholarly consensus.

It must have been a prudent step for a male God to appropriate one of the most popular local Great Goddesses. But today, Dharma is rarely worshipped in Bengal, but the so-called veil goddess continues to reign supreme. There must have been features to this new Great Goddess which resisted patriarchal appropriation.

It may not be wholly irrelevant to note here that the earliest concept of Dharma in Ṛg Vedic sources refers to Varuṇa, the Water deity as Dharma, as Professor Nick Sutton points out in one of his initial lectures in the term course on Dharma delivered under the aegis of the Oxford Centre for Hindu Studies ("A Study of Dharma"). There is an absence of any unbroken lineage of the cult of water deity in South Asia, but absence of evidence is not evidence of absence. The earliest recorded antiquity of the water deity must be traced back to the Harappan era, for

which the creative and sustainable principle of water held a cultic significance, as the Great Bath of Mohenjo Daro signifies; and as per Asko Parpopla, in one of the seals of the Harappan seated figure (the so called Paśupati, who as per scholarly consensus was a shaman or priest of the Harappan religion and was not always a man, and sometimes a woman), the seated figure is identified as the servant of the aquatic deity (qtd. in Ratnagar 25). This is not to hypothesize that the religious unconscious of the Dharma worship in medieval Bengal might have retained some remnants of the archaeomythology of the water deity when it celebrated Goddess Bāśulī. The fact remains that there is a significant connection between the Goddess Viśālākṣī and water.

Let us now look at the list of eight Viśālākṣī sites mentioned by Shibshankar Bharati, the popular writer of the stories and histories of Kālī temples of Bengal. As I pointed out earlier, he misses out a number of prominent Viśālākṣī sites. Nevertheless, his field visits remain useful for the purpose of this article, because in spite of being unaware of any connection between the theology of Goddess Viśālākṣī and Water Goddess/Lakṣmī, and in spite of being a lay observer lacking any academic training, he is nonetheless a religious initiate, a Goddess enthusiast, and his observations remain a valuable source of information about the lived tradition of the actual sites of worship of Goddess Viśālākṣī. Let me briefly produce the gist of Bharati's accounts of the eight Viśālākṣī sites of Bengal (303-335).

1. Viśālākṣī at Nanoor, Birbhum district, famous for the legendary medieval poet Baḍu Caṇḍīdāsa who worshipped the Goddess here. The local legends connect the Goddess to a nearby pond named Sarojā. The Goddess idol is that of Goddess Sarasvatī, originally a water goddess (figures 13&14).

2. Viśālākṣī Raṃkiṇī at the village Gopikantapur, Bardhaman district. There is again a sacred pond of the Goddess called Raṃkiṇīdaha which is a severed part of an old tract of the river Damodar. The iconic form of the Goddess is that of Kālī, and the Goddess idol is huge, having a size of twelve feet. There are reports of human sacrifice taking place as recent as 1837. The Goddess here is uniquely associated with Mahua tree. My observation here is twofold. First, Raṃkiṇī is generally a synonym for Cāmuṇḍā, which corroborates the point that the dhyānamantra of Viśālākṣī in Bāśulīmaṅgala mentions the Goddess to be identical with Cāmuṇḍā (we shall return to this point later). Secondly, the association with a tree, a very large idol, and human sacrifice – they all allude to primitive Yakṣī cults, so the Goddess here could really be Viśāla Yakṣī or, the Great Yakṣī. Further Sukumar Sen points out that the Great Goddess Durgā is called the first among the Yakṣīs in the Mahābhārata (*third vol* 155), which may be relevant for us.

3. Viśālākṣī at Anur, Hooghly district. Here the Goddess's name is also spelled as Viṣḷakṣmī. The Goddess is worshipped in aniconic form. There is no mention of any waterbody. My observation is that the explicit acknowledgement of the name of Lakṣmī is significant. I pointed out earlier that the majority of the local people of Rāḍḥa refer to the Goddess as Biśālokkhī in Bengali, which should be transliterated into Sanskrit as Viśālakṣmī, which is grammatically problematic, unless we consider this to be a combination of two Bengali words, Biśal and Lökkhī, which means Great Lakṣmī, which is Sanskrit should have been Viśāla Lakṣmī. But Viṣḷakṣmī is also correct as per Sanskrit grammar, and it literally means the Poison Lakṣmī. The term means Serpent Goddess Manasā, another prominent water deity seated on the lotus.

4. Viśālākṣī at Titagarh, North 24 Parganas. Reportedly the Goddess looks like Kālī, with four hands, one of which carries a severed head, another a sword, another assures fearlessness and

another gives boon (Abhayāmudrā, Varadāmudrā respectively), but the deity has the complexion of burning gold, and Her tongue does not stick out, unlike Kālī. The Goddess is worshipped on the banks of the Ganga river. My observations are: firstly, the Tantrasāra dhyānamantra speaks of the Goddess Viśālākṣī having the complexion of burning gold. Secondly, the iconography of Kācākāntī of Cachar in North East India is similar to this description provided by Bharati. Lastly, Viśālākṣī is a Riverine Goddess here.

5. Uttaravāhinī Viśālākṣī at Sheakhala, Hooghly district (figure 15). The Goddess was worshipped on the banks of the river Kauśikī during the medieval times, and the Goddess was popular, as She found a mention in Mukundarāma's Caṇḍīmaṅgala and Rūparāma's Dharmamaṅgala during the sixteenth century. The iconographic details of the Goddess are the following: She has the complexion of burning gold, has two arms, one holding a Khaḍga and the other with a bowl full of blood (earlier there used to be a skull cup). The Goddess puts one foot on the lying Mahākāla Bhairava, the other foot on the seated Baṭuka Bhairava, and further there is a severed head resting on the navel of Mahākāla, which is supposed to be that of an Asura named Niśumbha (slain by the Great Goddess in *Śrī Śrī Caṇḍī*). The newly made idol in 1933 has a height of seven feet, which was made by a sculptor from Kāśī, due to which the apparel of the Goddess resembles that of a North Indian lady, Bharati points out. The old river has long been dried out, and now in its riverbed stands a sacred waterbody called Bhogapukura (Bhogpukur in Bengali, literally meaning the pond of sacred offerings) near the temple of the Goddess. I do not add any observations here.

6. Caṇḍālakanyā or Caṇḍālamātā or Caṇḍālī Viśālākṣī at Krishnapur, Haripal, Hooghly district (figure 16). The Goddess has four arms, one of them carrying a Khaḍga. One foot of the Goddess is on the lying Mahādeva, the other foot is on Virūpākṣa Bhairava. No mention of any waterbody. My observation: Tantrasāra dhyānamantra refers to the Goddess as Caṇḍā (Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya 327).

7. Viśālākṣī of poet sage Kamalākānta at Channa, Bardhaman district. As I have already made a detailed case study of this temple, so I am skipping the descriptions of Bharati here.

8. Viśālākṣī, Ratanpur, Shyampur, Howrah district. The Goddess is a guardian deity of the Ratanpur village, and is called Ratanamālā. She has two arms, one carrying a Khaḍga and the other a bowl of nectar (suhāpātra), alternatively conceived as a bowl of blood (rudhirapātra). As per legend, Śrīmanta the famous merchant of maṅgalakāvya tradition came to this temple, which was then situated on the bank of Damodar river. The merchant arranged for beatings of large kettledrums in the honour of the Goddess which as a practice continues to this day, as every morning and evening, the drumbeats announce beginning of worship of the Goddess. Further, the Goddess's own Gajan festival is held annually at the time of Caitra Saṃkrānti. The river having changed its course is now far from the temple, but there is a large pond measuring five bighas on the eastern side of the temple which is considered to be sacred and blessed. I do not add any observations here.

A prominent absence in this list is probably the Viśālākṣī temple at Chhatna, Bankura (figure 17). Here, the Goddess has two arms, one holding a Khaḍga and the other Kharpara (skull cup). One foot of the Goddess is on the thigh of a prostrate Asura, and the other foot is on the head of another prostrate Asura (Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya 329). This is significant that instead of being called Bhairava, the men at the feet of the Goddess are called Asura here. In a familiar way this can imply that the Goddess is Asuradalanī, or the suppressor of the Asuras, but there

can be a second meaning where the sacred weight of the Goddess rests on the Asuras who essentially act as the Bhairavas of the Goddess.

The Viśālākṣī temple at Sinhet, Hooghly is another famous site. Here the Goddess has two arms, is flanked by Mahādeva, Lakṣmī, Gaṇeśa on one side, and Rāmacandra, Sarasvatī, Kārtikeya on the other. There are wall paintings of attendant ghosts standing behind the Goddess. She has the insignia of a Great Goddess, being visible with the retinue of attendant deities. One foot of the Goddess rests on a lying Mahādeva, while the other is on a severed head. A number of online sources claim that the temple was originally built in 1822, and there were many terracotta plaques on this temple which got lost at the time of a recent renovation in 2012. The temple structure is called Joḍabāṅglā. The temple is by the side of the River Kedāreśvara, the other bank of the river housing a temple of Goddess Manasā, locally celebrated as Viśahari. The Goddesses are celebrated as dual deities. ^{Note 5}

Gopendrakrishna Basu claims that the Goddess Viśālākṣī is not worshipped at home, that She is not a “gṛhadevatā” and is only worshipped at public places (58). But I have been able to find that the Goddess is indeed worshipped at the homes of Śākta devotees. One such idol’s image of the Goddess worshipped as a gṛhadevī and kuladevī at a household at Bagnan, Howrah district is attached (figure 18). So, the Goddess is not just limited to public places of worship.

There are many other temples of Goddess Viśālākṣī across South Bengal. Bāsulī is uniquely worshipped on a Pañcamuṅḍī āsana at the temple of the Goddess at Baradapalli, Medinipur district, where She is flanked by four attendants, namely Gaṇeśa and Kārtikeya, Jayā and Vijayā. The Goddess has four arms, and Her teeth are spread to the lower lips (Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya 330).

The presence of two Bhairavas gives the maṅḍala of the Goddess Viśālākṣī a unique theological significance (A popular depiction of Kāśī Viśālākṣī attached at the end – figure 22 – shows the Goddess holding miniscule Śivaliṅga and Gaṇeśa, indicating that the Goddess is theologically imagined with two male Gods), the detailed myth of which is not at all evident from the cryptic dhyānamantras. One of the Bhairavas is usually seated, and the other lying, but this is not a fixed pattern, and the frequent presence of severed head gives a unique dimension human sacrifice to Goddess Viśālākṣī. Any retrieval of the original myth of iconology would constitute a valuable contribution to our understanding of the Viśālākṣī cult.

Four: The Return of the Great Goddess

Goddess Viśālākṣī puzzles us. She presents a baffling collage of strange gaps and paradoxes. Viśālākṣī is worshipped by the legendary Vaiṣṇava poet Baḍu Caṅḍīdāsa (author of Śrīkṛṣṇakīrtana). She is explicitly hated by the later Vaiṣṇava poet Vṛndāvanadāsa who castigated the cult of Bāsulī (Sen *third vol* 260). Vṛndāvanadāsa bracketed the cult of Bāsulī with the cult of Yakṣa worship that used meat and alcohol.

Bāsulī is explicitly likened to a Ḍākinī in a poem that is attributed to Caṅḍīdāsa, though not in any negative way, as Gopendrakrishna Basu notes (53). The line says “Ḍākinī Bāsulī Nityā Sahacarī” which signifies that the Goddess might have been considered a Ḍākinī or an erudite lady who also had magical abilities in the spirit of Buddhist Tantra.

Viśālākṣī therefore reveals a very interesting trajectory of the waves of progress and regress. She is alternatively celebrated as the Great Goddess, and come under attack from Patriarchal religions. In spite of that, She must have continued to persist as the Great Goddess in certain pockets and enclaves of Śākta devotion to this day, not just through folk religious traditions, but also through scriptural and textual traditions. Does Her resilience allude to a deeper truth of archaic Great Goddess cults, which, in spite of being suppressed by patriarchal religions, still could be resurrected as New Great Goddess cults?

Probably Goddess Viśālākṣī has varying iconographies, has diffused and diverse traditions, local variations in Her worship which include different spellings of name as well as different names altogether as a result of this trajectory of upheavals. Her cult is anything but an organized religion.

The original myths of this Goddess are irretrievably lost, and conveniently substituted by the usual Purāṇic legends. If the temple of the Goddess is a Śakti/ Satī Pīṭha like that of Kāśī, then instead of any specific history and myth of the Goddess Viśālākṣī, to explain how a local Goddess from Bengal became the guardian deity there, the patriarchal story of the fragmented body of the consort Goddess Satī is perpetrated, where Viṣṇu and Śiva take centre stage, and the Goddess is relegated to a secondary position.

Sukumar Sen maintains that the archaic Great Goddess Nityā was resurrected during the medieval period of Sahaja Sādhanā, while Goddess Bāśulī appeared as the mentor of Sahaja sādhanā (*third vol* 176). The exact line that was written by Caṇḍīdāsa was: “Nityāra ādeśe Bāśulī colilo Sahaja jānābāra tare”, and Sen thinks that this line is extremely crucial for understanding the history of Goddess Viśālākṣī: She was originally an attendant Goddess to the archaic Great Goddess Nityā, a Water Goddess of antiquity, but soon Bāśulī became a Great Goddess in Her own right (*third vol* 251).

So, following Sen we can infer that the emergence of Bāśulī was closely associated with the Sahajayāna Tantra, and poetry of Sahaja Vaiṣṇava sage Baḍu Caṇḍīdāsa was a product of that cultural movement. And the primitive Vaiṣṇava unconscious memories of the archaic Lakṣmī (prior to appropriation) might remain a subtext in the familiar folk spellings of the name of the Goddess Viśālākṣī prevalent in large tracts of South Bengal overwhelmingly attesting that this Goddess is worshipped by the commoners as a Great Lakṣmī. The spelling Viśālākṣī is only prevalent among the educated elites. Commoners call the Goddess Biśālokkhī, let me reiterate as the risk of being repetitive.

Further, the sacred incantation given in Āgambāgīśa’s Bṛhad Tantrasāra too alludes to a certain aspect of this Great Goddess which resembles that of Lakṣmī (Sarvasaubhāgyajananīm mahāsampatpradām smaret), in which She is the Mother of all fortune and She is the giver of great wealth (Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya 328). Further, the name Viśālākṣī seems to be a gratuitous Sanskritization to such an extent that has not been able to infiltrate the sacred incantation and iconography of the Goddess in any major way. In the dhyānamantra of Tantrasāra and Bāśulīmaṅgala, the Goddess is never depicted as having large eyes. Barring the salutary incantation of the Goddess in Dharmapujā where the Goddess is worshipped as a Veil (Āvaraṇa), which says: Viśālavadanā devī viśālanayanojjwale/Daityamaṃsasprhe devī Viśālākṣī namohstute” (Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya 328), where the Goddess has large eyes and loves the meat of the Daityas (i.e. giants), there is practically nothing else in the prominent

dhyānamantras which suggests that She is the Lady with the Large Eyes. Her iconography in Bengal does not show any exorbitantly large eyes anywhere.

However, Sukumar Sen tries to come up with an innovative explanation behind the nomenclature Viśālākṣī, justifying the part of eyes. Sen points out that the different folk spellings of Goddess Nityā connected Her with Netra or eyes, which created the composite Godhead of Nityā Baśulī rechristened as Viśālākṣī or the Lady with the Large Eyes (*third vol 252*). Sen is either unaware of the Lakṣmī angle in folk spellings, or decides to ignore that completely, which does not cancel the merits of his arguments in any way though.

Further, Sen is very convinced that the name of Goddess Viśālākṣī is not any way linguistically derived from Vajreśvarī of Tāntrika Vajrayāna Buddhism (*third vol 259*). But Sen maintains that the Serpent Goddess Manasā and Goddess Baśulī are descended from one single Great Goddess who was the same as the Tāntrika Buddhist Goddess Cundā (*third vol 259-261*). Sadly, he does not elaborate on this issue, but this is an interesting line of exploration. Cundā is a moon Goddess. Her popular dhyānamantra compared the Goddess to the full moon of autumn, that of Kojāgarī Pūrṇimā, which is also when Goddess Lakṣmī is worshipped in Bengal (one can refer to Puspa Niyogi's article).^{Note 6}

One of the dhyānamantras of Goddess Viśālākṣī refers to Her face as the autumnal full moon, “śarādīndusuvadānām”, and this is the sacred chant which is used at the Nanoor temple, where the annual worship takes place during the Āśvina śukla pakṣa or Devīpakṣa, when Goddess Durgā is worshipped (Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya 329). The Nanoor idol being Sarasvatī, it shows points of transition between old Great Goddesses like Lakṣmī and Sarasvatī with new Great Goddesses like Cundā and Durgā.

Further, there is an alternative suggestion for the etymology of Bāsalī to be derived from sea salt, as the Sanskrit term Vasira means sea salt. This theory of Her nomenclature proposes that She was originally a marine goddess.^{Note 7}

A popular Vrata or folk ritual of ‘Alakṣmī Vidāya’ or ‘Ousting of Non-Lakṣmī’ narrates a story that prominently features fish and a crow, as the favoured inauspicious food item and the ultimate inauspicious manifestation of Alakṣmī respectively, as recounted by a speaker in a folk studies workshop organized at Asiatic Society, Kolkata in January 2025 that the present researcher attended. While I requested for citation, I was told that any common text carrying the Vrata Kathā of Alakṣmī Vidāya’ would contain the story. However, the Vrata of ousting of Alakṣmī is not a common one, and I have not been able to locate the same so far. But assuming the veracity of the speaker’s claim, the Non-Lakṣmī favoured fish, and assumed the guise of a crow, both of which might be significant from the perspective of Goddess religions of Bengal.

In Chandraketurgh, we find a Goddess carrying a pair of fishes (figure 12). And the bird Goddess is a recurrent theme in Bengal’s Goddess religion. In Pandu Rajar Dhibi, Bird Goddess was worshipped, as per the excavation report of Pareshchandra Dasgupta. In Aitareya Āraṇyaka, the Bengalis are called bird-like, or Vayāmsi, which Atul Sur considers to be a sign that the Bengalis worshipped Bird totem in early antiquity (21). Further, Crow is the standard vehicle of Mahāvidyā Dhūmāvātī, who is sometimes identical with Jyeṣṭhyā, having prominently inauspicious appearance. There is some compelling evidence that the worship of this bird goddess evolved eventually into the cult of the Goddess Kālī, which I discussed in “Archaeology of Prakṛti”. The fact that Goddess Viśālākṣī is often worshipped as Kālī (e.g.

Channa Viśālākṣī is worshipped as Kālī) is a significant aspect of Her cult. In the medieval text of Bāśulīmaṅgala the Goddess is identical with Cāmuṅḍā (we shall turn to that soon), a form of Kālī according to all scriptures, and as per history of the evolution of Goddess religions in Bengal, Cāmuṅḍā/ Carcikā was a crucial milestone in the evolution of Kālī.

Coda

Arguably, Bengal is home to the largest number of living Great Goddess traditions in South Asia and the world: almost all the goddesses who are worshipped in Bengal are Great Goddesses, which is a bit paradoxical, because the principles of greatness and supremacy and sovereignty are supposed to be exclusive and monolithic in any hierarchical structure or power. But in Bengal there is no hierarchy among the Goddesses. Each Goddess is supreme in Her own right, as the general Śākta devotee attempts at the reconciliation of these powerful almighty goddesses by arguing that they are different manifestations of the same creative feminine principle.

Further, in Bengal one cannot find the tradition of the worship of a group of small goddesses or consort goddesses or minor goddesses (we do not find a single Saptamātrkā temple or Cauṣaṭṭi Yoginī temple in Bengal). Not only the major Brahminical goddesses like Durgā, Kālī and Jagaddhātṛī, but even the mass goddesses like Śītalā, Manasā, Ṣaṣṭhī, Olābibi, Bonobibi, and the many different manifestations of Caṇḍī – all are worshipped by devotees as great goddesses. Even Lakṣmī and Sarasvatī, otherwise worshipped as attendant deities in the popular maṅḍala of Goddess Durgā, are worshipped as Great Goddesses during their annual days of worship, Kojāgarī Pūrṇimā/Śārad Pūrṇimā and Vasanta Pañcamī respectively.

In this article we are using the definition of the Great Goddess as given by Marija Gimbutas. A Great Goddess is the supreme, sovereign creatrix who is not a consort, or an attendant, or a mother or a daughter to any male deity. Viśālākṣī is a Great Goddess: her sacred incantations, her iconographies, her myths and the lived traditions of her worship establish beyond doubt that she is *the* Supreme, Sovereign Goddess.

This is the sacred incantation of Goddess Viśālākṣī from Tantrasāra by Āgambāgīśa which celebrates Her as a Great Goddess (qtd. in Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya 327-28):

Dhyāyeddevīm Viśālākṣīm taptajāmbunadaprabhām

Dvibhujāmbikām Caṇḍām khadgakhetaḥkadhāriṇīm

Nānālaṅkārasubhagām raktāambaradharām śubhām

Sadāṣoḍaśavarṣyām prasannāsyām trilocanām

Muṅḍamālāvalī ramyām pīnonnatapayodharām

Śavopari mahādevīm jaṭāmukutaṃḍitām

Śatruḥṣayakarīm devīm sādhakābhīṣṭadāyikām

Sarvasaubhāgyajananīm mahāsampatpradām smaret

The meditative incantation or *dhyānamantra* of Goddess Viśālākṣī depicts Her iconography: the Goddess's body has the aura of burning gold, She has two arms, has an extreme temperament of anger (Caṇḍā), carries sword and shield in Her hands, is adorned with ornaments, wears blood-red dress, is aged sixteen years, has a delighted visage, is three-eyed, wears garland of severed heads, is full-bosomed, is seated on a corpse, has a crown of matted hair, is a destroyer of enemies, fulfils the desires of one who meditates upon Her, is the mother of all fortune, is the giver of great wealth, is remembered by Her devotees (translation mine).

Parts of this incantation are produced by Jatindramohan Dutta in his article, in support his pithy claim that the worship of Goddess Viśālākṣī was far more prevalent during the medieval era when this *dhyānamantra* was composed, but Dutta unfortunately does not elaborate any further (564). It seems to me that he is alluding to the aspect of the Great Goddess as manifested in this incantation. The article by Dutta is on the rural gods and goddesses, published in the periodical magazine *Pravāsī*, apparently composed in a haste, which among other things contains a brief and incomplete list of the 12 temples of the Goddess Viśālākṣī which are found in different districts of south Bengal, where he mistakenly lists Nanoor under Bankura district (it should be Chhatna village of Bankura), and then again lists Nanoor under Birbhum district, this time correctly (564).

Periodicals publish in a rush (*Journal of Bengali Studies* included!), and such mistakes often occur due to a lack of time for cross-checking and proof reading. But this brief article by Dutta is valuable nonetheless, because this is probably the very first recorded discussion about the Goddess Viśālākṣī within the public sphere of Bengali elites. While Dutta relegates the Goddess to the marginal realms, for understandable reasons, he however vouches for a greater popularity of this Goddess during medieval antiquity, though he was unable to delve deeper into any detailed discussions. Further, a striking fact emerges from that brief list provided by Dutta, as one can note the high prevalence of the Goddess Viśālākṣī in the Hooghly district: six out of twelve temples of Goddess Viśālākṣī alone are in Hooghly in Dutta's list. This list is incomplete, and not at all exhaustive, as Dutta misses out on the names of a number of prominent Viśālākṣī temples of South Bengal. For example, the famous Viśālākṣī of Channa village of Bardhaman district, Whom the poet sage Kamalakanta worshipped, meditated upon and attained salvation, is altogether missing in Dutta's list. In spite of naming six Viśālākṣī temples of Hooghly, he still misses out a number of villages in this district which have prominent temples of this Goddess (Sinhet, for example). Also, the Goddess is worshipped under different names, and not always identified explicitly as Viśālākṣī; for example, Goddess Rājballabhī of Rajbalhat in Hooghly is a local form of Viśālākṣī (figure 19), which Dutta misses out. I am producing the list of Dutta here (564):

24 Parganas (North): 1. Kamarhati and 2. Titagarh.

Hooghly: 1. Arambagh (Bikrampur village) 2. Kamarpukur (Anur) 3. Sheakhala 4. Kolachora 5. Ilahipur in Haripal 6. Mathurabati in Jangipara

Bardhaman: 1. Ketugram

Bankura 1. Nanoor (sic)

Medinipur 1. Ghatal (Barada gram)

Birbhum 1. Nanoor

Going back to the iconographic incantations of the Goddess, Mukunda Mishra's *Bāśulīmaṅgala*, a medieval text from 1577 celebrates Bāśulī along the following lines:

Cāmuṅḍā nṛmuṅḍamālā dhṛta rudhirāmbara

Sarakta karpara kāti hāthe

Śoṇita sindhura jale kalpavṛkṣera mūle

Narapretāsane Bhagavatī (qtd. in Hangsanarayan Bhattacharya 327)

This description is actually a dhyānamantra, which shows the supreme goddess (Bhagavatī) Bāśulī to be identical with Cāmuṅḍā who is adorned with a garland of severed human heads, wearing blood-red dress, carrying in her hands bloodied skull-goblet and a saw, in a sea of blood, at the roots of the sacred tree of wish-fulfilment, the goddess is seated on a human corpse (translation mine).

The old Great Goddess Lakṣmī was a Water Goddess, as signified in the Purāṇic tale of Samudra Manthana, attested by the iconography where the Goddess is seated on a Lotus in the midst of water. The new Goddess Viśālākṣī has some crucial features of the Water Goddess in her incantation in Bāśulīmaṅgala. She is depicted to be seated on the Ocean water of blood. Interestingly, the same incantation also evokes the archaic Yakṣī Goddess, as Viśālākṣī reveals Herself by the Kalpavṛkṣa or the sacred tree of wish fulfilment.

Viśālākṣī is a resurrection of the old Great Goddesses. The point stands that all the new Great Goddesses like Durgā and Tārā are raised from the ruins of the old Great Goddesses. Rāḍḥeśvarī Viśālākṣī, the reigning deity of Rāḍḥa is a resurrection of a number of archaic Great Goddess cults, including Vārāhī, Yakṣī and Lakṣmī. She is known as Biśālokkhī. She is not an archaic Great Goddess, but is a reincarnation of the same. On this note let me finish this article.

End Notes

Note 1. For the religious and cultural significance of fish in the Harappan civilization: <<https://www.harappa.com/content/fish-symbolism-indus-valley-epigraphy-and-protohistoric-accounts>>, and <<https://www.harappa.com/script/parpola8.html>> For buffalo in the Harappan world: <<https://www.harappa.com/blog/buffalo-sacrifice>>, <<https://www.harappa.com/category/slide-subject/water-buffalo>>, <<https://www.harappa.com/blog/buffalo-seal-figures>>. Links accessed on 18 September 2025.

Note 2. As a popular article by Devdutt Pattanaik amply illustrates (“The ancient story of goddess Lakshmi”): “The ancient story of goddess Lakshmi – bestower of power, wealth and sovereignty”. <<https://qz.com/india/545655/the-ancient-story-of-goddess-lakshmi-bestower-of-power-wealth-and-sovereignty>>. Accessed on 18 September 2025.

Note 3. The priest-in-charge presiding over the worship of the Goddess on that particular Saturday during the prayer service happened to express severe displeasure when an elderly lady from an oppressed caste from a nearby village entered the sanctum sanctorum and tried to be close to the Goddess, when the priest scolded her rudely for this act of ‘impropriety’. It unfolded before my eyes, and I thought I should register this event in my field report. It is interesting to note that the famous poet sage Kamalākānta himself was a Brahmin, though he

was probably less 'Brahminical'. The panic reaction to assert that that the temple's sanctum sanctorum is strictly meant for Brahmins and forward castes, and is off limits for the oppressed castes, is paradoxical to say the least. The fundamental philosophy of Goddess cults and Tantra oppose casteism and patriarchy.

Note 4. Sabhā Parva of Mahābhārata mention this state of Karvaṭa along with Tāmralipta and Suhma while describing the war expedition of Bhīma to the east. In all likelihood, Karvaṭa was in modern day South Bengal. Refer to this discussion <https://www.historydiscussion.net/history-of-india/history-of-bengal/bengal-from-earliest-times-to-till-1202-a-d/5729#:~:text=In%20the%20epics%2C%20however%2C%20the,banks%20of%20the%20river%20Kosi.>

Note 5. A number of online sites and social media pages in Bengali offer information of the Goddess Viśālākṣī worshipped at Sinhet, Hooghly. The place name is claimed to have descended from Senahāti. <https://www.facebook.com/100067073894911/posts/%E0%A6%AC%E0%A6%BF%E0%A6%B6%E0%A6%BE%E0%A6%B2%E0%A6%BE%E0%A6%95%E0%A7%8D%E0%A6%B7%E0%A7%80-%E0%A6%AE%E0%A6%A8%E0%A7%8D%E0%A6%A6%E0%A6%BF%E0%A6%B0-%E0%A6%B8%E0%A6%BF%E0%A6%A8%E0%A7%87%E0%A6%9F%E0%A6%B8%E0%A7%87%E0%A6%A8%E0%A7%87%E0%A6%9F-%E0%A6%B9%E0%A7%81%E0%A6%97%E0%A6%B2%E0%A6%BF%E0%A6%B9%E0%A7%81%E0%A6%97%E0%A6%B2%E0%A6%BF-%E0%A6%9C%E0%A7%87%E0%A6%B2%E0%A6%BE%E0%A6%B0-%E0%A6%AA%E0%A7%8B%E0%A6%B2%E0%A6%AC%E0%A6%BE-%E0%A6%A6%E0%A6%BE%E0%A6%A6%E0%A6%AA%E0%A7%81%E0%A6%B0-%E0%A6%AC%E0%A7%8D%E0%A6%B2%E0%A6%95%E0%A7%87%E0%A6%B0-%E0%A6%8F%E0%A6%95%E0%A6%9F%E0%A6%BF-%E0%A6%97%E0%A7%8D%E0%A6%B0%E0%A6%BE%E0%A6%AE-%E0%A6%B8%E0%A6%BF%E0%A6%A8/1638508526321689/> accessed on 18 September 2025.

Note 6. Goddess Cundā was worshipped by the first Pāla emperor Gopāla, as per the description of Lāmā Tāranātha, a fact recorded by Alaka Chattopadhyay in her study (257). The present author had the privilege of being acquainted with the modern day descendants of the Pāla dynasty who claim descent from King Mahīpāla II, whose ancestor settled in the Sylhet region during the medieval times, and the same is attested in the medieval text of Śrīhaṭṭa Vaidya Kūlapañjikā as this clan belongs to the Maudgalya gotra of the Vaidya caste, the clan surname being Dāsa/Dāśa. In Mañjuśrīmūlakalpa the Pāla emperors have been referred to as "Dāsajīvinah" (Ray 322), which might be an attestation of the claim of this family. This family worships Goddess Kālī on the day of Kojāgarī Pūrimā, which is the annual family festival for them. Debraj Pal Chowdhury, a Pāla descendant sent me an image of their annual worship of the Goddess (figure 20). The connection between Cāmuṇḍā/Kālī and Goddess Lakṣmī is ancient. The night of Kārtikī Amāvasyā celebrated as Dipanvitā Kālīpūjā is also when Goddess Lakṣmī is worshipped as per Tantrasāra of Agambāgīśa. There is a Cāmuṇḍā idol on the wall of Paraśurameśvara temple at Odisha where the vāhana of the Goddess is an owl, which is otherwise associated with Lakṣmī (figure 21).

Note 7. This article in Bengali by Asit Das claims that Bāsulī was a Goddess of sea salt, and connects Her with the salt deities of ancient Greco-Roman world.

<https://pagefournews.com/salt-goddess-mata-basuli-part-ii-asit-das/>. Accessed on 18 September 2025.

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Figures

Figure 1. An idol deserted by the wayside at Durgakona, Barak Valley, North East India (near Assam University, Silchar). Images by author.

Figure 2. Goddess Kācākānti of Cachar, and the author at the temple of the Goddess.

Figure 3. “Viśālākṣī Kālī Mother” temple at Channa village. This is where poet-sage Kamalākānta attained siddhi.

Figure 4. Statue of Kamalākānta on his legendary Pañcamuṇḍī. Viśālākṣī temple complex at Channa, Bardhaman. Photo by author.

Figure 5a, 5b, 5c (left to right): Bhairava temple by the main entrance. Bhairava temple on the rear. Horse Figurines inside the rear temple

Figure 6. Copper Hoard Culture (2nd to 3rd Millenium) Boar, which could be considered 'pregnant' with Harappan unicorn. Sourced from [internet](#)

Figure 7. Pāla period Vārāhī (11th century), prominently holding a fish in the lower right hand. [Asian Art Museum, San Francisco](#).

Figure 8. Goddess Vārāhī riding a buffalo. [Odisha state museum.](#)

Apparent Anarchy of Folk Spellings!

The collage shows various spellings of the goddess's name in Bengali, such as 'বিশালক্ষ্মী', 'বিশালক্ষ্মী', 'বিশালক্ষ্মী', and 'বিশালক্ষ্মী'. It also includes a YouTube video thumbnail for 'Bishalakh Vishalaxmi' with Bengali text: 'শ্রীমদ্ভগবৎ বিষ্ণুসংহিতায় পিতার অথবা হৃত্যায় পিতা কর্তৃক বিতাড়িত হয়ে সাতশত যুদ্ধরূপে অস্তর দিয়ে সমুদ্রযাত্রা করেন এবং ত্রিশর্পী ধীপে অবতরণ করে সেখানকার অধিবাসীদের পরাজ করে দক্ষাধীপ অধিকার করেন। তিনি ত্রিশর্পী বা দক্ষাধীপ অধিকার করে সেখানকার রাজকন্যাকে বিবাহ করেন এবং সেখানকার রাজ্য হন। রাজা হওয়ার পর তিনি ওই ধীপের নাম রাখেন সিংহল।' and 'সিংহলের বন বিশালক্ষ্মী মন্দিরে খেতে হলে তারকেশ্বর লোকালয়ে উঠে নিস্তুর বৈশাখ নাম্ন। চৈতন্যের দক্ষিণ দিকে এ.এ. মন্দির বোঝ থেকে টোটা বা অটোতে উঠুন। নাম্নে পুরুষোত্তমপুর ব্রাহ্মণপাড়ায়। ঐ মন্দিরে বা বিশালক্ষ্মী মন্দির। কেউ কেউ বলেন বিশালক্ষ্মী।' and 'মন্দিরটি ঊঁচু মিত্রবৈদ্যের উপর প্রত্যক্ষ, দক্ষিণমুখী, চারচালা মন্দির। পূর্বপুত্রের সামনে দ্রিখিলান প্রবেশমণ্ডকে অগ্রসর অলিন্দ। দুটি প্রবেশমণ্ড বর্তমানে ভাঙাটুকরা। অলিন্দের সামনে রোয়াক। পূর্বদিকে রোয়াক একটিই প্রবেশমণ্ড। মন্দিরের সামনের দিক টোটারে অলংকরণে অলংকৃত। মন্দিরের শিবরঙ্গেশ পাছ হওয়াতে মন্দিরের অলংকর্মেই ফটি হয়েছে। ফটি হয়েছে টোটারে অলংকরণেও। কিন্তু খিলানের

Figure 9. The apparent anarchy of Bengali spellings which corroborate that common Bengalis address Viśālākṣī as some form of Lakṣmī

Figure 10. The author with a local friend at Vana Viśālākṣī temple. This is an empty temple, devoid of any idol. Selfie by author.

Figure 11. Goddess Lakṣmī from Chandraketugarh (1st/2nd Century BC) standing on a lotus. Sourced from [Met Musuem](#), which mistakenly addresses this plaque as Goddess Durgā.

Figure 12. Goddess from Chandraketugarh (1st/2nd Century BC), carrying a pair of fishes, sourced from [Santa Barbara Museum of Art](#)

Figure 13. New idol of Goddess Viśālākṣī at Nanoor. She is Sarasvatī. Sourced from [Kalikhetro Andolon](#)

Figure 14. Old idol of Goddess Viśālākṣī at Nanoor. She is Sarasvatī. Sourced from [Kalikhetro Andolon](#)

Figure 15. Goddess Uttaraṅghri Viśālākṣī at Shekhala, sourced from [Matshonyay blogzine](#).

Figure 16. Caṅḍālakanyā or Caṅḍālamātā or Caṅḍālī Viśālākṣī at Krishnapur, Haripal, Hooghly. Sourced from [Vidyaragni facebook page](#)

Figure 17. Viśālākṣī at Chhatna, Bankura. Sourced from [internet](#)

Figure 18. Goddess Viśālākṣī worshipped as a gr̥hadevī and kuladevī at Bagnan, Howrah. Photo courtesy Dr Raktim Mukherjee.

Figure 19. Goddess Rājaballabhī at Rajbalhat, Hooghly. Sourced from [wikimedia](#)

Figure 20. Worship of Goddess Kālī on Kojāgarī Pūrṇimā by the family that claims descent from Pāla Emperor Mahīpāla II. Photo sent by Debraj Pal Chowdhury, a Pāla descendant.

Figure 21. Goddess Cāmuṇḍā with owl as vahana. This is part of a Saptamātrkā panel on the wall of Paraśurameśvara temple, Odisha. Sourced from [instagram](#)

Figure 22. Popular depiction of Kāśī Viśālākṣī sourced from [pinterest](#). No similarity with Bengal Viśālākṣī as such. But note the presence of two male Gods, Śiva and Gaṇeśa in the two upper hands of the Goddess, as if representing the two Bhairavas.